

Employee Performance and Emotional Intelligence in NBFC's

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Abstract

Emotional intelligence is the key to the success of every one's personal and professional life. So the success depends upon the ability of the people to manage their emotions and the ability to understand the emotions of others. Employees who are emotionally inept have difficulty managing their emotions. As a result, they frequently act rashly, believing that the consequences of their actions will have no effect on them or those around them. The study's main goal is to examine the relationship between emotional intelligence and employee work performance. Out of a total of 500 responses, 474 were complete. Respondents were chosen using a Snowball sampling technique rather than non-probability sampling. Employee performance is improved by the Emotional Intelligence factor.

Introduction :

In every organisation, the employees have to deal with different people with different background, knowledge and emotions. If the employees want to deal successfully with these people they should have good emotional intelligence. As persons we are not able to control our emotions, then we will be left alone in the society. So in the same way in workplace also employees will be thrown out alone if they do not know to manage their emotions. For the successful career life an employee should have the support of his peers, superiors as well as customers of that organisation. To have all these people in his hand the employee should have the ability to understand their emotions and also he must be able to control his own emotions.

Employees in the organisation must be able to think rationally before taking any decision which is related to a particular act. The decisions taken with emotional feeling will always be incorrect. Without thinking rationally if they take any decision will mislead them. So we say that every employee should be free from his emotions before making decisions. So at work place they must be able to manage their emotions. So here the concept emotional intelligence have a prominent role. If the employee is not in a position to manage the emotions then his

thinking capacity will be overwhelmed by emotions. Also the emotional intelligence helps the employee to understand the emotions of others, which helps them to point out the reasons for their behaviour. And the employees can easily communicate with others.

To become emotionally intelligent one must know his emotions and must be able to control and manage his emotions. And also he must be able to understand the emotions of others. This type of intelligence always helps the employee to lead his career life successfully in the organisation.

Literature Reviews :

Hasan, N.S., (2022)¹. He proclaims that in order to achieve high levels of employee performance, the tourism industry—which relies heavily on human labour—needs skilled workers with important employee characteristics. Employees in the tourism industry frequently face situations that necessitate a high level of emotional intelligence in order to ensure customer satisfaction, so the industry requires workers with a high level of emotional intelligence. Emotional intelligence employees can make decisions to improve performance by changing their behaviours in a desired manner and can improve their negotiation skills, making it important for raising employee performance. Emotional intelligence, as a result, has a positive impact on employee performance in Egyptian tourism businesses.

Statement of the Problem :

The significance of Emotional Intelligence in the organisational environment especially in the work place settings is getting high. Learning and practicing emotional intelligence brings a quality in an employee to self direct the impulsive behaviour in a positive direction. The ability to act wisely in human relationship requires that the employee must apply three emotional intelligence skills. They are Effective Communication, Emotional Self Control and Reflection of Interpersonal Intelligence. Effective Communication is the way in which emotional intelligence skill can be exerted. Emotional self control is a part of emotional intelligence skill which helps a person to manage his anger and anxiety. Reflection of interpersonal intelligence is the ability to understand and appreciate the differences in the context of dealing with others. These skill sets of the emotional intelligence permit an employee to work effectively in groups and teams. It is the responsibility of an organisation to create a conducive organisational climate to ensure the continuous improvement of the emotional skill sets of the employees. The emotional skill of an employee is needed to abreast the past changes happening in the work and business environment. These are more visible in the place of market and technology. So for the successful running of the day today affairs of the organisation as well as the long term survival, the involvement of talented employees are a must. Along with the talent and knowledge, they should have the ability to control their emotions and aspirations. From this discussion on emotional intelligence related to the organisational environment one can surely understand the relationship between emotional intelligence and employee performance. Therefore creating a positive emotional intelligence in the behaviour pattern of employees shall result in excellent employee performance in organisations. This study is undertaken to examine the relationship between emotional intelligence and employee performance in the organization.

This study is intended to analyse the emotional intelligence of the employees of Non-Banking Financial Institutions (NBFCs) who undergoes hectic workload and the nature of

their work is pressure oriented. As a result employee attrition rate is moving in an upward direction. This leads a big loss both to the organisation and the employees. Also the employees are found to be more stressful. In such context the study of emotional intelligence finds to be more worthy. And this study is particularly focuses on the relationship between emotional intelligence and the employee performance in a dynamic service sector like public Non-Banking Financial Companies (NBFCs) in South Tamilnadu. Many studies are already conducted by focusing on emotional intelligence and work environment of the different industries but there is a gap exists in research focusing on the relationship between emotional intelligence and employee performance of Non-Banking Financial Companies (NBFCs).

Objectives :

1. To study the main factors affecting the job performance of employees working in non-banking financial institutions.
2. To identify the factors influencing the Emotional Intelligence of Employees in Non-Banking Financial Companies (NBFCs).

Scope of the Study :

The scope of the present study is confined to the Non-Banking Financial Companies (NBFCs) in South Tamilnadu. The unit of the study (respondents) is the employees of NBFCs. The study is particularly focused on those elements constituting to the emotional intelligence as well as assessing the degree of influence of emotional intelligence on the work performance of the employees.

Methods :

In this study, the researcher utilised a descriptive cross-sectional research design. A combination of primary and secondary data was collected to meet the stated objectives of the study. The minimum sample size required for this study is 386, but the researcher has targeted 500 respondents who are working in non banking financial institutions of Kanyakumari district based on the results of a pilot study. In the current study, 474 complete responses were utilised out of the total of 500. Respondents were selected using non-probability sampling, but they were chosen using a Snowball sampling strategy. On the basis of the entered data, Confirmatory Factor Analysis and Structural Equation method were used to obtain statistical conclusions.

Result and Discussion :

Emotional Intelligence impact on work performance with a mediator of organisation commitment, When the work time is more, the employees get exhausted to carry over their work dynamically. In this context, the study has penetrated in to the working hours factor.

S.No	Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percent
1	Up-to 8 Hours	94	19.7
2	8 -10 Hours	250	52.4
3	More than10 Hours	130	27.9
	Total	474	100

Pertaining to working hours factor, the above table presents the emotional intelligence and employee performance of non banking financial institution (Kanyakumari). The overall respondents taken for the study are 474. The respondents who work up to 8 hours are 94 and their percentile value is 19.7 and the respondents who work between 8 to 10 hours are 250 and their percentile value is 52.4. The respondents who work more than 10 hours are 130 and their percentile value is 27.9. It is clear from the table that the maximum respondents work between 8 to 10 years.

Suggestions :

1. More than half of the employees working between 8-10 hours. This make them more stress and anger is also anther problem that is being faced by the employees.
2. Make it safe for employees to express their emotions, and they will work harder and better. People tell the truth to those who withhold judgement, keep secrets, and keep their cool.
3. Intimacy with a boss, employee, or coworker can flood the workplace with emotional memories, causing thoughtful, reasonable professionals to lose objectivity and resentment in onlookers.

Conclusion :

In this research, we can conclude that Emotional Intelligence is an important factor for employees to manage their emotions. According to this study, employees with high Emotional Intelligence competencies outperform employees with low Emotional Intelligence competencies. Emotional intelligence plays a crucial role in the performance of the employees as revealed by the present research. The pillars of any organization are the employees. Maintaining their emotional intelligence is very essential for any organization. When the Emotional Intelligence of the employees is low, it can negatively affect not only the employees, but also the company at large. It has been widely observed that in any industry, the job commitment factor improves employees' social lives as well as the organization's productivity as a result of appreciation and reward. Managers play an emotional role in organisational development because they manage employees and their work lives.

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